

least twenty times slow as compared to that in presence of the organic acid. The correction for auto-decomposition has, therefore, not been applied. Again, the reaction is of first order with respect to cobalt(III) and fractional with respect to the organic acid whereas it is second order with respect to cobalt(III) in absence of it. Hence, it is clear that the loss of cobaltic ions in presence of *n*-valeric acid is mainly due to its direct oxidation by cobalt(III). It may be mentioned that Clifford and Waters¹ reported the kinetics of the oxidation of propionic acid by cobalt(III). Our observations are similar to their findings.

Hence, for the oxidation of *n*-valeric acid by cobalt(III) also, an inner sphere mechanism involving the rapid reversible formation of a cobaltic complex may be advanced. The complex then breaks down slowly with liberation of free alkyl radical, which then undergoes further rapid reactions. Thus

The formation of a little aldehydic product from *n*-valeric acid was established by the isolation of its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone.

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References

1. A. A. CLIFFORD and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 2796.
2. J. K. STHAPAK and S. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 347.
3. J. K. STHAPAK and S. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 391.
4. J. K. STHAPAK and S. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 48, 331.

Kinetics of the Oxidation of Malic Acid by Peroxydisulphate

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THE kinetics of the oxidation of malic acid by peroxydisulphate ion has been studied by Kumar and Saxena¹ who found the reaction to be bimolecular in the initial stages. A probable free radical mechanism leading to a bimolecular rate law was proposed by these authors according to which the reaction should proceed through $CO_2\cdot$ radical.

The esr studies of the reaction², however, did not agree with the proposed mechanism of the above authors as no $CO_2\cdot$ free radical was detected in such systems. The only free radical detected in these systems was $\cdot CH_2CH(OH)COO^-$. This suggests that the mechanism proposed by the above authors should be altered and modified. A new mechanism involving $\cdot CH_2CH(OH)COO^-$ radical is proposed below which leads to the experimental rate law.

According to the above mechanism, the rate of the peroxydisulphate decomposition can be expressed by equation (9)

$$\frac{-d[S_2O_8^{2-}]}{dt} = k_1[S_2O_8^{2-}] + k_6[\cdot CH_2CH(OH)CO_2][S_2O_8^{2-}] \quad (9)$$

On applying the steady state treatment to the above mechanism,

$$\frac{d[S\bar{O}_4^{\cdot -}]}{dt} = \frac{d[O_2CCH(OH)CO_2]}{dt} = \frac{d[\cdot CH_2CH(OH)CO_2]}{dt} = 0$$

the concentration $[\cdot CH_2CH(OH)CO_2]$ can be calculated as

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$$[.CH_2CH(OH)CO_2] = \frac{-(k_2k_6[H_2O] + k_1k_8) + \sqrt{(k_2k_6[H_2O] + k_1k_8)^2 + 8k_1k_4k_6k_8[\text{Malic acid}]}}{4k_6k_8} \quad \dots (10)$$

On neglecting the negative root, Equation (10) can be re-written as

$$[.CH_2CH(OH)CO_2] = \frac{(k_2k_6[H_2O] + k_1k_8)}{4k_6k_8} \left\{ -1 + \left(1 + \frac{8k_1k_4k_6k_8}{(k_2k_6[H_2O] + k_1k_8)^2} [\text{Malic acid}] \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\} \quad \dots (11)$$

Since experiments are done at low malic acid concentrations and water is present in large excess, it can be assumed that

$$\frac{8k_1k_4k_6k_8 [\text{Malic acid}]}{(k_2k_6[H_2O] + k_1k_8)^2} \ll 1$$

Therefore equation (11) can be simplified as

$$[.CH_2CH(OH)CO_2] = \frac{2k_1k_4 [\text{Malic acid}]}{(k_2k_6[H_2O] + k_1k_8)^2} \quad \dots (12)$$

On substituting the value of $[.CH_2CH(OH)CO_2]$ from (12) in (9), we get

$$-\frac{d[S_2O_8^{2-}]}{dt} = k_1[S_2O_8^{2-}] + k^1[S_2O_8^{2-}] [\text{Malic acid}] \quad \dots (13)$$

Where k_1 is the first order rate constant for the thermal decomposition of peroxydisulphate in absence of any substance and k^1 is bimolecular rate constant for the oxidation reaction. Thus, equation (13) gives the same rate law as expected from the experimental results of Kumar and Saxena¹.

References

1. K. KUMAR and L. K. SAXENA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 612.
2. W. C. VASUDEVA, *J. Chem. Soc. (Perkin II)*, 1975, 697.
3. R. O. C. NORMAN, P. M. STORREY and P. R. WEST, *J. Chem. Soc. B*, 1970, 1087.
4. R. J. FABER and G. K. FRAENKEL, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1967, **47**, 2462.
5. J. Q. ADAMS, S. W. NICKSIC and J. R. THOMAS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1966, **45**, 664.

Relation Between Lattice Energy and Melting Points of 3d Metal(II) Oxides

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In a family of closely related crystalline compounds where the same potential energy function is applicable on fusion, a direct proportionality between the lattice energy ($-U_o$) and absolute melting point^{1,2} (T_m) is expected. Since different members under this condition are in a similar state of mutual interaction, they usually conform to a general constancy of the ratio $-U_o/T_m$. This trend has been well-maintained for the oxides of s and f block metals^{1,2}, respectively. It was, therefore, thought meaningful to investigate the family of 3d metal(II) oxides from the above view point and compare the results of $-U_o/T_m$ ratios for s, d and f block metal oxides. The desired data of Born-Haber lattice energy⁴ and absolute melting points^{5,6} for the oxides of present interest were taken from literature and the values of $-U_o/T_m$, thus calculated, are recorded in Table I.

Regression analysis :

Excluding the ratio of $-U_o/T_m$ for FeO as recorded in Table I (the reason being given under

TABLE I—RELATION BETWEEN $-U_o$ and T_m OF 3d METAL(II) OXIDES

Metal oxides*	$-U_o$ (k cal mole ⁻¹)	T_m (K)	$-U_o/T_m$ (k cal mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
TiO	949	2023	0.47
VO	947	ign.	—
MnO	929	1923	0.48
FeO	954	1693	0.56**
CoO	978	2073	0.47
NiO	995	2263	0.44
CuO	1004	1999 dec.	—
ZnO	985	2243	0.44

* $-U_o$ and T_m data for SnO and CrO are not available in literature.

** Significant trend.

Results and Discussion), the proposed relation for other members of the family have been subjected to regression analysis. Assuming a linear relation between $-U_o$ and T_m , one can write :

$$T_m = a + bU_o \quad \dots (1)$$

Using the criteria of least squares and solving the normal equations, one obtains the final form of eqn. (1) as :

$$T_m = 4.99U_o - 2721.33 \quad \dots (2)$$

Thus, the regression coefficient (b) of the concerned relation is 4.99 with its estimated standard error equal to ± 1.07 . Moreover, the correlation

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